

METHODOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SPEECH AND THINKING OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS BASED ON A CREATIVE APPROACH

Abdullayeva Mavlyuda Aribovna

Lecturer at the Department of Pedagogy and Psychology of Pedagogical Faculty, Andijan State
Pedagogical Institute

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Abstract. *The article talks about the methodological aspects of the development of speech and thinking of students of higher educational institutions using a creative approach. Based on an analysis of the literature devoted to the problem, methodological principles for the development of speech and thinking of future teachers are determined. In addition, the content and forms of cooperation between students and professors and teachers were discussed.*

Keywords: *thinking, speech, language, creative approach, pedagogical technology, methodological principles, interactive learning.*

Thinking is a creative human activity in which one can study the most complex features of things and events, foresee events, and make predictions. Thought exists in organic relationships, that is, thought is a spiritual phenomenon. It is realized only through language, in the form of a material event (sound waves, graphic lines), it takes on a form that other people can directly perceive and feel, and becomes a means of exchange of ideas between people.

Based on our experience and observations, it is planned to improve the content of education, aimed at finding solutions to the following problems in the development and implementation of modern standards for the development of speech and thinking of students of higher educational institutions:

- establishment and integration of activities in mutual cooperation with higher educational institutions of foreign countries; (online communication, distance learning, advanced training for teachers based on government grants;)
- modernize education and achieve free mobility of education with mutual cooperation of student teachers and parents;
- creation of acceptable uniform rules and a system of requirements for the higher education management system;
- achieving unity of requirements for knowledge, skills and qualifications and systems for their assessment in accordance with international standards;
- creating opportunities for students to communicate freely during all types of activities;
- instead of traditional teaching methods, modern, innovative teaching methods should be developed and integrated into the educational process;

Also, as long as pedagogical processes exist, educational technologies will continue to develop and improve. From this point of view, changes have been made and improved approaches, laws and principles. A.K. Kolechenko highlighted some aspects of the fundamental principles of pedagogical technology:

- the principle of educational preparation;

- the principle of achieving efficiency in training, development, education;
- the principle of one hundred percent feedback;
- the principle of constant repetition;
- the principle of optimal mental arousal;
- the principle of ensuring maximum participation of students in the educational process;
- the principle of focusing on the zone of proximal development [1,43].

According to the above scientists, it is possible to improve the process of development of speech and thinking of university students by providing feedback during interactive modeling of public (holidays, events), collective and individual forms of communication. activities, i.e. based on a classroom approach according to current and future plans, as well as the organization of the educational process taking into account the young and individual characteristics of students, are of great pedagogical importance.

According to an analysis of psychological literature, one of the outstanding characteristics of students is their activity, curiosity and imitation [2,87]. It is worth saying here that the growth of speech among students of higher educational institutions is a process directly related to the cultural level of the family. In the process of perceiving something, this synthesis manifests itself in perceptual actions, in attention, in the management and control of the plan of internal and external actions and situations, as well as in memory, in memorizing material and the ability to connect the internal and external structure of memory. And in thinking it clearly manifests itself as the unification of methods of working on practical issues into one common process. On the basis of this, human intelligence is formed and developed.

According to N.U. Bikbaeva, in the process of developing students' speech and thinking, the student's sensory abilities, manifested in the perception of objects and their characteristics, are of particular importance in the development of environmental knowledge. In the context of the development of their sensory abilities, creative abilities aimed at solving certain problems related to thinking and imagination quickly develop [3].

In D.R. Babaeva's scientific research, simple moral norms and personal rules take precedence over the speech educational process. These rules and regulations govern personal morality. Different relationships arise with the people around you, and these relationships are based on different motives. The development of coherent speech among peers when studying the environment turns them into individuals who are distinguished not only intellectually, but also morally motivated [4,11].

M. Montessori's book "Different Children" directly reflects the sensory, intellectual, creative process of learning about the world, realized through thinking. Based on the idea "Help me do it myself," M. Montessori pays special attention to the development of students' speech and thinking processes through independent creative games. In his opinion, through games, students actively learn new knowledge, relying on existing knowledge, without directly turning to experience each time. The thinking process is based on relationships between things and events [5,129].

Based on the analysis of the above literature and research by methodologists and psychologists, we can say that in educational psychology there are many studies devoted to the study of the processes of independent thinking of students and the creation of pedagogical and psychological patterns of various processes. Many researchers recognize that the development of modern trends in the education of students in higher educational institutions has a positive effect

on students' speech. But, unfortunately, the development of student speech and thinking of university students based on a creative approach has not become the subject of pedagogical analysis. The main system for the formation of creative activity of any person begins with students of higher educational institutions. In our opinion, the thought process, which creates the opportunity to study the most complex features of things and events, to foresee events, to make predictions, exists in an organic connection with language.

Based on this, we can say that one of the important factors in the development of students' dialogical speech is the development of their speech culture. Another important factor is "education of thought"; the richer the inner world of a thinker, the higher the level of his thinking.

The article by M. Bakina "Modern students, modern games" [6,24] states that language is a direct form of thinking, and it is the thinking of students that is expressed in speech through the processes of comparison, analysis and synthesis. activate and develop your thinking processes. In such processes, students compare different things and try to carry out analysis and synthesis. Therefore, in the context of the development of speech and thinking of students of higher educational institutions based on a creative approach, it is necessary to strictly adhere to the following pedagogical goals: education of spiritual and moral virtues, formation of moral principles. , its historical stages, continuity and continuity. I did it. In that:

- his acceptance of existing national values in the development of students' speech and thinking, their knowledge and understanding contributes to the development of students' thinking abilities;

- formation of a spiritual and moral worldview in the development of personality based on strengthening ideological immunity, understanding and acceptance of national values;

- the development of students' speech and thinking in the process of adhering to the beliefs of a healthy lifestyle is of great pedagogical importance.

Based on a truly creative approach, the foundations of a culture of a healthy lifestyle and a healthy worldview were formed in the context of the development of speech and thinking of students of higher educational institutions. But real life, that is, practice, is the factor that differentiates the concepts of development of speech and thinking of students. In real practical life, if the worldview of students is formed on the basis of moral standards from the age of preschool education, then moral and ethical virtues are easily and effectively formed in students, and the moral worldview forms the basis of thinking process.

That is, the development of students' creative abilities through non-traditional work methods[7,18], the development of dialogical speech, studying with new ideas and new enthusiasm, meaningful rest, enriching the daily routine with interesting and useful activities. This is considered one of the urgent and important tasks. Therefore, the creative potential of future teachers lies in meaningfully spending time outside the educational process, providing them with both physical and mental rest, instilling in their minds the national idea, patriotic feelings, national and universal values. It is believed that this depends on many aspects.

Develop students' creative abilities, natural sciences, etc. Timo - pedagogy is important for the formation of philosophical views and high efficiency of the educational process.

In the well-known traditional educational process, professors and teachers do not have the opportunity to control the level of knowledge of each student. The educational process allows teachers to quickly manage the educational activities of students.

In the process of education, the traditional authoritarian style will change. As a result, faculty members occupy advisory positions. The objectives of this process are to create favorable conditions for students' self-expression, to open a wide path for students to show initiative, to provide the opportunity to independently solve problems and collect new information. base. Based on the ideas presented, we can say that this is a special form of organization and development of students' educational activities. The joint activity of students during the learning process allows them to contribute to the assimilation of educational material. They share knowledge, ideas, and methods of action with each other. Such educational activities are carried out in an atmosphere of mutual goodwill and create favorable pedagogical conditions for students to acquire new knowledge, as a result of which they get the opportunity to develop their communication skills. Communication skills include listening to colleagues or teammates, comparing and evaluating different points of view, participating in discussions, and finding solutions to problems. They gain the ability to work in a team, thereby experiencing a sense of security in the process of learning together, understanding each other and having the opportunity to achieve personal success.

It is also possible to motivate students to creative activity by using technologies that are compatible with the educational process, highlighting organizational, content, procedural, orienting situations in the educational process. Each of these cases corresponds to certain ideas. The first aspects of the educational process are meaningful generalization, coordination of educational materials, integration of educational subjects, and consolidation of didactic skills.

Another characteristic of teaching methods is the creation of goodwill, harmony and emotional and spiritual unity in the relationships of students. As a result of the use of interactive methods, students appear as equal participants in the perception process, and their experience serves as a source of learning activity. At the same time, teachers do not provide students with ready-made knowledge, but encourage them to independently search. In the process of interactive learning, in contrast to traditional learning, the mutual actions of students and teachers change. In particular, the activity of the professor-teacher is replaced by the activity of students. The task of teachers is to encourage students to take initiative. Professors-teachers perform the duties of a subject teacher who provides information to students and a consultant who helps them. Are interactive methods universal? got a question. It should be noted that interactive teaching methods can never replace lecture classes. However, they create the opportunity to successfully assimilate lecture material and, in this process, help shape students' thoughts, attitudes and behavioral skills. Conflicts between goals and inclinations form the basis of professional development as the basis of students' creative abilities. These conflicts play an important role in ensuring the movement of tendencies towards the goal. This requires students to develop natural aptitudes for self-education. The emergence of students' needs thus serves as an important resource for creating creative activity in them. This creates the basis for students to develop a system of actions aimed at self-improvement and regular improvement. The characteristic aspects of such actions in most cases serve to determine the content of professional goals. On the other hand, pedagogical activity appears in the eyes of the student as a personal, deeply realized value, self-improvement, and creative activity needs to be shown.

Experts distinguish two types of student self-assessment methods. The first method is to adjust your own level to the results achieved, and the second is to compare the assessment of yourself and others about yourself. However, when using these methods, mutual assessment is not always possible. In some cases, students overestimate themselves. Mostly, students who set

themselves high-level tasks face difficulties in this area. Students who are creative and have creative abilities always compare their results with the results achieved by their peers and objectively evaluate themselves.

The primary method for properly assessing students' creativity should not be to compare their results with those of their ideal teachers. This method of work should be taught to students from the first academic year. The simplest and most reliable way to form a professional ideal among students is to accustom them to reading specialized literature, introducing them to the life and professional creative activity of mature teachers. The correct formation of an ideal among students is an important condition for the formation of a professional ideal among students. formation of their creative abilities.

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